

VOID CONTROL IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES: A MODEL BASED ON FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICAL/CHEMICAL PRINCIPLES

JONATHAN R. WOOD AND MICHAEL G. BADER

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Surrey,
Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, United Kingdom.

ABSTRACT

The problem of porosity has been addressed in relation to process modelling of composite materials. Models based on mass diffusion theory successfully represent the growth and collapse of gas bubbles in an epoxy resin. The steady-state diffusion equations require the diffusion coefficient and solubility of the mobile species within the resin pre-cursor. These parameters are affected by changes in temperature and/or pressure. A method of measuring the diffusion coefficient of gases in the resin has been outlined and the temperature dependence of the diffusion coefficient has been correlated to the viscosity of the medium using a free volume approach.

Keywords: porosity, modelling, diffusion, polymer-matrix, viscosity, free-volume

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective behind the processing of thermosetting matrix composite materials is to produce void-free laminates of the specified dimensions with the optimum degree of cure of the resin. Porosity can occur due to changes in the fabrication procedure and can have a detrimental effect on the mechanical properties of the final part [1]. In order to process high performance structural laminates consistently, it is necessary to identify the material and processing inter-relationships which are critical to the production of a void free laminate and formulate models that can aid the elimination of such porosity.

Bubbles present within the resin will grow or collapse as the temperature and hydrostatic pressure in the resin are varied during the cure cycle. Bubble behaviour is influenced by such changes in accordance with the ideal gas law equations and due to the diffusion of mobile species across the bubble/resin interface, i.e. gaseous species in the bubble diffuse into the resin or dissolved gases in the resin diffuse into the bubble. An increase in temperature or decrease in pressure will cause the gas within the bubble to expand resulting in bubble growth. Changes in pressure and temperature can also have a pronounced effect on the solubility of mobile species in the resin which may influence not only the magnitude of the driving force for diffusion but also the direction of the concentration gradient. As an increase in temperature also causes an increase in the diffusion coefficient, mass transfer of molecularly mobile species will also increase resulting in more rapid bubble growth or collapse depending on the direction of the diffusion gradient relative to the host bubble [2].

Models based on mass diffusion theory have been investigated [2,3] and it is considered that entrapped bubbles can be collapsed or suppressed from growing by manipulating the process variables during the curing operation, i.e. it is possible to influence bubble behaviour by changing the processing temperature and pressure. To implement these models successfully, a number of input parameters and their respective interactions with the process variables need to be evaluated before it is possible to predict the growth or collapse rate of gas bubbles in the resin. The material parameters include the diffusion coefficient and the solubility of the mobile species in the liquid resin which are functions of temperature and/or pressure. As a model is only as successful as the accuracy and availability of the input data it is beneficial to have relationships that can predict these input parameters and/or their interaction with the changing process variables from fundamental materials data or from more accessible physical quantities. The rationale behind the investigation is that the relationships and the input parameters required for a void model can be translated to other systems with minimal materials characterisation and to different composite processing options. By minimising empiricism it is also easier to confront the problem that there is no universal cure cycle and thus find the optimum schedule within the window dictated by the cure and consolidation processes.

2. DIFFUSION-CONTROLLED BUBBLE KINETICS

The diffusion of gases in a liquid depends primarily on the driving force for the diffusion and the diffusion coefficient of the species in the liquid. The driving force can be expressed in terms of a concentration gradient which influences the flux of molecules into or out of a bubble. The concentration profiles for growing or collapsing spherical bubbles are time-dependent and affected by the concentration of mobile species within the bubble C_o , the concentration at the interface C_s and the concentration in the bulk liquid C_∞ . Surface tension forces also aid the collapse and hinder the growth of bubbles while the diffusion coefficient D determines the rate of growth or collapse due to molecular transport in the fluid medium.

The mathematics of bubble diffusion is closely analogous to the theory of heat conduction from a perfectly conducting sphere in an infinite isotropic medium [4]. The exact modelling of bubble kinetics requires the solution of many coupled time-dependent partial differential equations for which complete analytical solutions are not generally available. Likewise, many of the physical properties are not known with sufficient accuracy to justify the excessive computational time that would be required for a numerical analysis. Fortunately some assumptions and simplifications can be made which allow a mathematical treatment to be used for typical composite systems [5].

It is possible to obtain Epstein and Plesset's [6] differential equation for the bubble radius from Fick's laws assuming a spherically symmetrical bubble.

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = -\frac{D(C_s - C_\infty)}{\rho R} \left(1 + \frac{R}{(\pi Dt)^{1/2}}\right) \quad \dots (1)$$

where, R is the radius of the bubble, ρ is the density of the gas within the bubble (which is equivalent to the C_o) and t is time.

Equation 1 shows that a gas bubble in a liquid-gas solution will grow or shrink by diffusion according to whether the solution is oversaturated or undersaturated, i.e. the sign of $(C_s - C_\infty)$. For the problem of composite processing, where the cure schedule is sufficiently long to render the transient term negligible, it is proposed that the term $R/(\pi Dt)^{1/2}$ be neglected, which leads to the asymptotic steady-state solution

$$R^2 = R_0^2 - \frac{2D}{\rho}(C_s - C_\infty)t \quad \dots (2)$$

where, R_0 is the bubble radius at $t=0$.

This assumption facilitates the solution of the highly non-linear equation 1 and becomes increasingly applicable to a composite processing route where bubble sizes are generally small and elevated temperatures (higher diffusion coefficients) are common practice. A further modification to the quasi-stationary and the steady-state assumption is the inclusion of surface tension forces which become increasingly important as the bubble size decreases and an important consideration when the time to collapse a bubble is of interest. For the special case of where $C_s=C_\infty$, i.e. a saturated solution, the steady-state assumption including the surface tension forces is

$$1 - e^3 + \delta(1 - e^2) = \left(\frac{3\delta}{2}\right)x^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

where, $e=R/R_0$, $x^2=(2Dd/R_0^2)t$ and $\delta=\tau/[R_0\rho(\infty)]$, $d=C_s/\rho(\infty)$, $\tau=2M\gamma/R_gT$

and $\rho(\infty)$ is the density of the gas with a gas/liquid interface of zero curvature, M is the molecular mass of the gas, γ is the surface tension of the resin, R_g is the universal gas constant and T is the temperature.

The time for complete solution is given by

$$x^2 = \left(\frac{2}{3\delta}\right)(1+\delta) \quad \dots (4)$$

In a saturated solution equations 1 and 2 predict indefinite stability whereas when surface tension forces are also considered diffusion controlled collapse is predicted.

3. EVALUATING THE INPUT PARAMETERS

The diffusion equations in Section 2 clearly require the diffusion coefficient and the concentration gradient to be known during the processing cycle to predict the bubble radius at any time. These are not generally known quantities for most resin systems and also are not parameters that are measured as part of the manufacturers materials characterisation programme. Even the surface tension of most resin pre-cursors is a quantity that is not readily available without independent measurement. The utility of a process model that can be used as a "shop floor" tool, is improved if these parameters and their respective interaction with the changing processing conditions can be easily measured or preferably predicted from known data. The following investigates the diffusion coefficient required for the diffusion model where bubbles containing a non-condensable gas grow or collapse as a consequence of the gas diffusing into or out of the host bubble.

3.1 Experimental Procedures

All experiments were performed on an unmodified bisphenol-A/epichlorohydrin resin (Shell 828) which had an epoxy group content of 5.128moles/kg [7]. The resin was thoroughly degassed in a vacuum oven at 333K and stored in a desiccator. Volatile weight losses,

measured on a thermogravimetric balance, were found to be minimal ($\leq 0.1\text{wt}\%$) after the degassing operation. The gas used in the bubble experiments was pure dry nitrogen. This was readily available and the use of a single gas facilitated subsequent modelling.

The viscosity of the resin was measured using a simple falling sphere method and was found to be extremely temperature dependent having a room temperature value (293K) of 23-26 Pa.s. This method was limited to a temperature of 353K at which point the sphere velocity was too high to attain consistent readings. A

capillary tube method was used for the higher temperature (lower viscosity) data [8]. The tube was calibrated against glycerol which had a known viscosity (1.5 Pa.s at 293K). The resin was sucked into the capillary tube and one end was temporarily sealed to allow the resin to reach the required temperature. The seal was then broken and the flow time for the resin to pass through the tube under gravity was measured and correlated to the viscosity. All measurements were within $\pm 10\%$ of the mean value.

The surface tension was measured using a capillary rise method over a range of temperatures (293-373K). The room temperature value of 0.035N/m in air is in agreement with most gas/polymer systems [9] and was found to decrease slightly over the temperature range investigated but not significantly with respect to the calculated experimental errors ($\pm 10\%$). The solubility of nitrogen in resin was measured using a vacuum method and was found obey Henry's law [2,3,5].

A novel method was used to measure the gas diffusion coefficient over the temperature range of interest. The fundamental theory behind the experimentation is that the rate of solution of a stationary gas bubble in a liquid is governed by both the solubility and the diffusion coefficient of the gas in the liquid. The liquid at the bubble surface maintains a gas concentration equal to the saturated solution concentration at the local pressure. If the surrounding fluid has a lower concentration, then gas molecules diffuse outward, thereby depleting the solution at the bubble surface and permitting more gas to dissolve. By applying the steady-state solution to Fick's law as described in section 2, an equation is obtained giving the bubble radius as a function of time (equation 2). The parameters of this equation are the solubility and the diffusion coefficient; if the solubility is known then the diffusion coefficient may be determined by fitting the equation to experimental radius vs. time data (figure 1).

Small nitrogen bubbles were injected into a saturated resin in a glass cuvette using a hypodermic syringe and monitored with time by optical microscopy. Bubbles were monitored until complete collapse which ranged from a few minutes to several hours over the temperature range investigated. The pressure and temperature were constant throughout the duration of each test. A saturated resin was used since it was possible to make up reproducible solutions thus eliminating the variable of the dissolved gas concentration in the bulk from the

Figure 1 Temperature dependence of bubble collapse rate.

theoretical analysis. This reduced a possible source of error in the calculations. The surface tension forces are solely responsible for the collapse of gas bubbles in a saturated system since they increase the gas pressure in the bubble and thus lead to the increase in the dissolved gas concentration in the resin at the surface of the bubble. The collapse times were substituted into equations 3 and 4 and the diffusion coefficient was retrieved.

The main advantage of this technique is that it offers a convenient means to determine diffusion coefficients of gases in transparent liquids. The input parameters required to determine the diffusion coefficient are also easily measured, i.e. the gas solubility and the surface tension forces. The accuracy was determined as a percentage deviation from the mean which was found to be $\pm 20\%$. This is not significantly less accurate than other more intricate methods of determining the diffusion coefficient, e.g. diffusion coefficients for oxygen in water, using a volumetric uptake method, range from 1.9×10^{-9} to $2.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ at 298K which is $\pm 15\%$ from the mean value [10]. Deviations from run to run were attributed to convection currents in the liquid caused by temperature and concentration gradients.

Figure 2 WLF plot for the viscosity of the resin reduced to 293K.

4. COMPARISON OF VISCOSITY AND DIFFUSION DATA

Many attempts have been made to predict the diffusion coefficient and/or its dependence on temperature from molecular considerations. Although expressions based on such models would seem to offer the advantage that the necessary parameters should be predictable from the inherent properties of the penetrating molecule and the resin, all models to date have one or more "adjustable parameters" except for some specific systems over limited temperature ranges [11,12]. Models based on free volume theory have a definite advantage in that they can relate other measurable parameters such as the viscosity to the diffusion coefficient. The viscosity of the resin is of critical importance to composite processing in terms of infiltrating the reinforcement and determining the optimum time to apply pressure to consolidate the laminate. As the viscosity of the resin is a required and generally known parameter a correlation between the diffusion coefficient and the viscosity is extremely valuable.

The viscosity can be mathematically represented using the basic form of the WLF equation [13] which is in the form of a shift factor a_T and is simply the ratio of the viscosity at a temperature T relative to that at a reference temperature T_0 . The expression states

$$\log a_T = \frac{-C_1(T-T_0)}{C_2+T-T_0} \quad \dots (5)$$

where T_0 is a reference temperature and C_1 and C_2 are constants characteristic of T_0 and to a lesser extent the polymer.

If the reference temperature is the glass transition temperature of the polymer T_g , C_1 and C_2 take the values of 17.44 and 51.6 respectively which are considered to be "universal constants". This assumes that the glass transition temperature is an iso-free volume state.

Hence a plot of $(T-T_o)/-\log a_T$ versus $T-T_o$ should be linear with a slope $1/C_1$ and an ordinate intercept of C_1/C_2 . Figure 2 shows a plot of this type reduced to 293K for the experimental data. This was chosen as the reference temperature as it was the lowest temperature measured and had least scatter. A linear regression has been used to find the best fit line through the low temperature points. The two high points were not used in the regression as these temperatures are well in excess of the applicability of free volume theory and will be better represented by an energy barrier approach.

The data falls on a good straight line giving $C_1=7.69$ and $C_2=125.58$. These values can now be used to determine the constants at the T_g using the interrelations

$$C_{1\eta} = \frac{C_1 C_2}{C_2 + T_g - T_o} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$C_{2\eta} = C_2 + T_g - T_o$$

Substituting the empirical and the universal constants into both equations yields values for T_g of 223K and 219K respectively. These values for the T_g are comparable to the that calculated from the semi-empirical molecular mass dependence of epoxy pre-polymers [14]. The viscosity can also be represented by Doolittle's semi-empirical equation [15],

$$\eta = \eta_o \exp\left(\frac{B_\eta}{f(T)}\right) \quad \dots (7)$$

where B_η and η_o are constants and $f(T)$ is the temperature dependence of the free volume and can be expressed in the linear form,

$$f(T) = f(T_g) + \alpha(T - T_g) \quad \dots (8)$$

and $f(T_g)$ is the free volume fraction at T_g and α is the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients above and below the T_g . Fitting this equation to the viscosity data and using the universal constants it was found that B_η was 0.98 which is very close to the accepted value of unity.

One can modify the Doolittle equation by noting that the diffusion coefficient is inversely proportional to the frictional resistance in accordance with molecular friction theory [16], i.e. diffusion and viscous flow will be governed by the same frictional constant. In a very crude approximation one can say that this is proportional to the viscosity of the medium so that

$$D = D_o \exp\left(\frac{-B_d}{f(T)}\right) \quad \dots (9)$$

The pre-exponential constant is a parameter that depends on the size and shape of the penetrant molecule. The parameter B_d can be interpreted as the efficiency of the use of the available free volume in the diffusion process [17].

It is interesting to compare the \ln viscosity and diffusion coefficient vs. $1/T$ graphs. As one can not compare "activation energies" apart from at a specific temperature (comparison with experimental data is difficult with the need to draw tangents to the curve) it is more useful to consider Doolittle's equations (equations 7 and 9) for the viscous and the diffusion process directly. Figure 3 shows the application of the Doolittle equation for viscosity and the modified form for the diffusion coefficient with the experimental data. The coefficients B_d and B_η are unity within experimental error. The ratio of the Doolittle

Figure 3 Free volume theory applied to viscosity and diffusion data.

coefficients B_d and B_η is therefore also unity implying that the efficiencies in utilising the free volume by a mass transport process relative to momentum transfer are similar. This is interesting in that one would expect that a small molecule such as nitrogen would diffuse much faster in resin than the diffusion of a resin molecule required for viscous flow. It implies that the temperature dependence of the diffusion process is characterised by the mutual action between molecules of the resin and not of that between the dissolved nitrogen and the resin. At higher temperatures there is a departure from free volume theory which is in agreement with the empirical observation that free volume theory is only applicable to the point where the temperature dependence is so great that it is independent of the molecular structure.

This interesting result is considered in terms of molecular considerations. If the solute molecule is larger than the solvent then the motion of the solute can not be described in terms of vibrations about an equilibrium position and displacements of the latter but must be described by Brownian motion. In this case it is clear that there will be a relationship between the viscosity and the diffusion coefficient of the solute. If the solute molecule is of comparable size to the solvent it will diffuse at the same rate as the solvent since the diffusive transport is completed only by the jumping of a neighbouring solvent molecule into the remaining void. This is not implying that a nitrogen molecule is of comparable molecular size to a resin molecule. A semi-quantitative argument says that polymers do not flow as single rigid units [18]. Instead small segments jump from one equilibrium position to another. The effective activation energy for diffusion is therefore not only a consequence of the transition of the diffusant to a new equilibrium position but also the motion of the resin into the initial position, i.e. the effective activation energy for diffusion must refer to the whole complex of particles participating in the transition which for dilute solutions, as in the case of permanent gases in polymers, can not markedly differ from that governing viscous flow.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The apparent relationship between the diffusion of nitrogen and the viscosity of the medium is extremely fortuitous since the gas diffusion coefficient in the resin is a required and more easily interpreted but not readily available parameter. It should also apply for any gas/resin system where the free volume is not significantly disturbed by the penetrating molecule, i.e. low

penetrant concentrations. A knowledge of the viscosity of the resin and application of free volume theory enables calculation of the temperature dependence of the diffusion coefficient for any temperature in the processing cycle. The gas diffusion coefficient should also be predictable in a curing system where the viscosity is initially decreased by raising the temperature and then dramatically increases due to the crosslinking reaction. It will then be possible to determine the point at which the bubble is effectively "frozen" into the laminate and so place limits on the time required to eliminate bubbles in the cure cycle. It must be remembered that the diffusion coefficient can only be as accurate as the model that predicts the viscosity, i.e. if free volume theory applies over a limited temperature range in the processing cycle then this will also be the limit of the calculated diffusion coefficient. At higher temperatures the relationship between the viscosity and the diffusion coefficient may still prevail but the chemical structure of the polymer will play an increasingly important role compared to the non-specific vitrification phenomenon, i.e. the viscosity can no longer be considered to be temperature dependent due to free volume considerations alone.

REFERENCES

1. Hull, D., *Introduction to Composite Materials*, Cambridge University Press, 1981, Chap.7, pp145.
2. Wood, J.R., *Quantitative Process Modelling of Transport Phenomena and Bubble Dynamics for Polymer Matrix Composite Materials*, PhD. thesis, University of Surrey, England, 1992.
3. Wood, J.R., Bader, M.G., *Modelling the Behaviour of Gas Bubbles in Epoxy Resin*, Proceedings of 8th International Conference on Composite Materials, 10-M, 1-9, 1991.
4. Crank, J., *The Mathematics of Diffusion*, Oxford University Press, 1956, Chap.6, pp84.
5. Wood, J.R., Bader, M.G., *Void Control for Polymer Matrix Composites (1)*, submitted to Composites Manufacturing.
6. Epstein, P.S., Plesset, M.S., *On the Stability of Gas Bubbles in Liquid-Gas Solutions*, Journal of Chemical Physics, Vol.18, No.11, pp1505-1509, 1950.
7. Shell Resins, *Epikote Technical Manual*, E.P. 1.1.12, 3rd Edition, 1987.
8. Flory, P.J., *Viscosities of Linear Polyesters - An Exact Relationship between Viscosity and Chain Length*, Journal of the American Chemical Society, Vol.62, pp1057-1070, 1940.
9. Wu, S., *Estimation of the Critical Surface Tension for Polymers from Molecular Constitution by a Modified Hildebrand-Scott Equation*, Journal of Physical Chemistry, Vol.72, No.9, 1968.
10. Himmelblau, D.M., *Diffusion of Dissolved Gases in Liquids*, Chemical Review, Vol.64, pp527-550, 1964.
11. Meares, P., *The Diffusion of Gases Through Polyvinyl Acetate*, Journal of the American Chemical Society, Vol.76, pp3415-3422, 1954.
12. Brandt, W.W., *Model Calculation of the Temperature Dependence of Small Molecule Diffusion in High Polymers*, Journal of Physical Chemistry, Vol.63, pp1080-1084, 1959.
13. Williams, M.L., Landel, R.F., Ferry, J.D., *The Temperature Dependence of Relaxation Mechanisms in Amorphous Polymers and Other Glass-forming Liquids*, Journal of the American Chemical Society, Vol.77, pp3701-3707, 1955.
14. Aleman, J.V., *Glass Transition Temperature of Epoxide Pre-Polymers*, Journal of Polymer Science, Vol.18 (Polymer Chemistry Edition), pp2561-2565, 1980.
15. Doolittle, A.K., *Studies in Newtonian Flow II - The Dependence of the Viscosity of Liquids on Free-Space*, Journal of Applied Physics, Vol.22, pp1471-1475, 1951.
16. Bueche, F., *Viscosity, Self-Diffusion, and Allied Effects in Solid Polymers*, Journal of Chemical Physics, Vol.20, No.12, pp1959-1964, 1952.
17. Peterlin, A., *Dependence of Diffusive Transport on Morphology of Crystalline Polymers*, Journal of Macromolecular Science, Phys., B11(1), pp57-87, 1975.
18. Meares, P., *Polymers: Structure and Bulk Properties*, Van Nostrand, 1965, Chap.9, pp237.